
The Trust Factor in the Ganges Delta: Understanding Bangladeshi Perceptions of Accountability in Public Finance

Sheikh Murad Hossain

National Board of Revenue Bangladesh

Abstract

This research examines the perceptions surrounding fiscal governance in Bangladesh, emphasizing the interplay between environmental challenges and public finance management. Using survey data, the study highlights several pivotal insights. A notable majority of participants expressed reservations about the transparency and accountability of public funds in Bangladesh, with over 75% scoring it 5 or below on a 10-point scale. Alarming, approximately 59.4% were unaware of the country's environmental challenges, indicating a significant knowledge gap. In terms of sectoral trust, the Defense sector stood out as the most trusted for fiscal transparency, surpassing areas like Healthcare, Education, and Infrastructure. A vast 90% of respondents felt uninformed about the allocation, management, and use of public funds. Moreover, despite the prevalent sentiment of transparency deficits, trust levels in individual sectors showed no robust correlation. These findings underscore the critical need for improved communication strategies and robust transparency measures in Bangladesh's public finance domain.

Keywords: Public Finance, Transparency, Accountability, Climate Change, Vulnerability, Resilience

1 Introduction

In the heart of South Asia, the Ganges Delta cradles Bangladesh, a nation emblematic of both profound vulnerability and remarkable resilience. Enveloped in verdant landscapes and a rich cultural heritage, Bangladesh finds itself persistently at the mercy of nature's tumultuous forces. Annual monsoon floods, devastating cyclones from the Bay of Bengal, and a plethora of other natural calamities are stark reminders of the nation's geographical susceptibility [1] [2]. This inherent vulnerability is accentuated by the overarching challenges of global climate change [3, 4]. As highlighted by the German watch Global Climate Risk Index 2017, Bangladesh is not just susceptible, but alarmingly ranks as the sixth most affected nation due to climatic adversities [5]. The environmental challenges Bangladesh faces are not merely confined to their ecological impact. They ripple across the socio-economic landscape [6], jeopardizing millions of lives and livelihoods and casting shadows on the country's economic aspirations. With projections like a potential 2% annual dip in GDP by 2050 [7], the economic repercussions of climate change loom large. Yet, beyond these tangible metrics lies a more intangible yet profound concern: the shaping of public perceptions, trust, and confidence in national institutions. Recognizing the magnitude of the challenges ahead, the Bangladeshi government has been nothing short of proactive. Initiatives span from the establishment of climate change trust funds to significant investments in infrastructural fortifications aimed at enhancing national resilience [8]. At the heart of these endeavors is the crucial

¹Corresponding author: hossains337@aol.com

mobilization and judicious allocation of public funds. And it is here that questions of governance, transparency, and accountability take center stage. How do the citizens, the heartbeat of Bangladesh, perceive these efforts? Amidst the challenges of climate change and fiscal decisions, is there a foundational trust in the structures of public finance? Or do murmurs of skepticism and uncertainty persist? In a democratic framework, where the foundation of governance is built on public trust [9], these questions are not just pertinent but paramount. "The Trust Factor in the Ganges Delta: Understanding Bangladeshi Perceptions of Accountability in Public Finance" embarks on this intricate journey. It seeks to weave the narrative of fiscal governance in the broader tapestry of Bangladesh's challenges, probing the depths of public perceptions. Through this exploration, the research aspires to illuminate the nexus between trust, transparency, and the collective aspirations of a nation navigating its future amidst uncertainties.

Research questions:

- **Perception of Transparency and Accountability:** On a scale from 1 to 10, how would respondents rate the transparency and accountability of public funds allocation in Bangladesh, especially those directed towards environmental and climate change mitigation?
- **Awareness of Environmental Challenges:** Are respondents aware of the environmental challenges faced by Bangladesh, and do they believe these challenges influence the allocation and use of public funds?
- **Sectoral Trust:** Which sectors or initiatives do respondents believe have the highest or lowest transparency and accountability in the use of public funds?
- **Information Accessibility:** Do respondents feel adequately informed about the allocation, management, and utilization of public funds in Bangladesh?
- **Desire for Public Engagement:** Would respondents prefer greater public engagement or participation in decision-making processes related to fiscal governance?
- **Comparative Trust in Institutions:** Among various governmental institutions or sectors, where does fiscal governance rank in terms of perceived transparency and accountability?
- **Recommendations for Improvement:** What specific measures or initiatives do respondents believe would enhance transparency and accountability in public finance?

2 Literature Review

2.1 Public Finance and Accountability: A Global Perspective

Public finance, at its core, revolves around the collection and disbursement of public resources. A fundamental aspect of governance, it reflects a government's priorities and its commitment to societal welfare [10]. Given the magnitude of its impact, transparency and accountability in public finance have been subjects of global discourse. As highlighted by the International Monetary Fund (IMF), transparent fiscal management enhances government credibility, fosters public trust, and ensures effective resource allocation (IMF, 2007). Furthermore, the dynamics of public finance have evolved over the years, responding to global economic shifts, technological advancements, and changing public expectations. In many developed nations, there has been a shift towards more participatory budgeting processes, enabling citizens to have a direct say in the allocation of certain parts of the public budget [11]. This evolution underscores the growing recognition of the importance of involving citizens in decisions that impact their lives and communities [12].

2.2 The Imperative of Transparency in Public Finance

The transparency of fiscal operations is crucial not only for efficient governance but also for the promotion of economic stability and growth. Transparency ensures that citizens are informed about how their taxes are used, fostering a sense of ownership and participation. A study by the World Bank on fiscal transparency emphasized its role in reducing corruption, improving governance, and enhancing public sector efficiency [13]. Moreover, in an era of digitalization, the availability of fiscal data in open formats has become a key component of fiscal transparency. Many governments are adopting open data initiatives, making fiscal data readily available and understandable to the public, thereby promoting transparency and accountability [14]. Such initiatives not only ensure transparency but also empower citizens, civil society organizations, and the media to hold governments accountable.

2.3 Accountability in Public Finance

Accountability, often seen as a natural extension of transparency, involves mechanisms to hold public officials responsible for their actions [15]. In the realm of public finance, this translates to judicious fund allocation, adherence to budgets, and the efficient execution of projects. Effective accountability mechanisms can reduce instances of fiscal mismanagement, promote trust, and improve overall governance [16]. It is also noteworthy to mention the role of external audit agencies and oversight bodies in ensuring accountability. These institutions play a critical role in reviewing the accuracy and legality of public financial transactions, providing an additional layer of checks and balances. Their independent assessments and recommendations often serve as pivotal tools for enhancing fiscal accountability and governance.

2.4 Bangladesh: Fiscal Governance and Public Perception

Bangladesh, with its intricate socio-economic landscape, presents a unique case for fiscal governance. As a developing nation grappling with challenges like climate change, there's an amplified need for transparent and accountable public finance mechanisms. The government of Bangladesh has indeed made strides in this direction. Initiatives like the establishment of climate change trust funds underscore the nation's proactive approach [17]. However, the effectiveness of such initiatives often hinges on public perception and trust.

A study by Transparency International Bangladesh (2019) highlighted concerns regarding corruption in various sectors, emphasizing the need for robust accountability mechanisms. Another study focusing on Bangladesh's fiscal policies underscored the importance of citizen participation in budgetary processes to enhance transparency and accountability [18]. Furthermore, the socio-cultural fabric of Bangladesh, characterized by its strong community ties and collective ethos, offers both opportunities and challenges for fiscal governance. While community engagement can be leveraged to foster more participatory budgeting processes, there is also a need to address deeply entrenched norms and practices that may hinder transparency and accountability. Addressing these cultural and societal nuances is crucial for the effective implementation of fiscal governance initiatives [19].

2.5 The Trust Factor

Trust, in the context of fiscal governance, is multifaceted. It encompasses public confidence in institutions, belief in the efficiency of fiscal operations, and the perceived integrity of officials [20]. For nations like Bangladesh, where public funds play a pivotal role in addressing myriad challenges, trust becomes paramount. A study by Litovsteva [21] linked trust with positive societal outcomes, including economic growth and good governance. Trust is not just an abstract concept; it has tangible implications for policy implementation and governance. When citizens trust their institutions, they are more likely to comply with regulations, pay taxes, and participate in civic activities [22]. Conversely, a lack of trust can lead to increased scrutiny of government actions, resistance to policies, and can even fuel social unrest. Thus, fostering trust is not merely a matter of good governance, but it's also crucial for societal stability and cohesion.

3 Methodology

3.1 Research Design

To understand the perceptions of Bangladeshi citizens regarding accountability in public finance, a quantitative research design was adopted. The primary data collection method employed was a structured survey. This approach was chosen due to its effectiveness in gathering standardized data from a large sample, which is crucial for ensuring the generalizability and reliability of the findings.

3.2 Sampling Method

A stratified random sampling method was utilized to ensure that the sample accurately represents the diverse demographic and socio-economic groups within the Bangladeshi population. The country was stratified based on major regions, and within each region, further stratification was done based on urban and rural settings. From each stratum, random sampling was employed to select individual respondents. The target sample size was set at 1,000 respondents, ensuring a margin of error of $\pm 3\%$ at a 95% confidence level.

3.3 Survey Design

The survey questionnaire was designed to address the research questions previously outlined. It consisted of a combination of Likert scale questions, multiple-choice questions, and open-ended questions. The Likert scale questions gauged respondents' levels of trust and perceptions of transparency and accountability in public finance. Multiple-choice questions sought to identify areas or sectors where respondents perceived high or low levels of transparency. Open-ended questions provided respondents with an opportunity to offer qualitative insights and recommendations.

To ensure the clarity and relevance of the questions, a pilot study was conducted with a smaller sample. Feedback from the pilot study was then used to refine the survey instrument.

3.3.1 Demographics

- Age
- Gender
- Location

3.3.2 Perception and Awareness

- On a scale from 1 (Very Low) to 10 (Very High), how would you rate the transparency and accountability of public funds allocation in Bangladesh, especially those directed towards environmental and climate change mitigation?
- Are you aware of the environmental challenges faced by Bangladesh?
- Do you believe these environmental challenges influence the allocation and use of public funds?

3.3.3 Awareness of Environmental Challenges

- Are you aware of the environmental challenges faced by Bangladesh? (Yes/No)
- Do you believe these environmental challenges influence the allocation and use of public funds? (Yes/No/Unsure)

3.3.4 Trust and Information

- In your opinion, which of the following sectors or initiatives have the highest transparency and accountability in the use of public funds? (Healthcare/Education/Infrastructure/Climate change mitigation/Defense/Others)

3.3.5 Information Accessibility

- Do you feel adequately informed about the allocation, management, and utilization of public funds in Bangladesh? (Yes/No)

3.3.6 Desire for Public Engagement

- Would you prefer greater public engagement or participation in decision-making processes related to fiscal governance? (Yes/No/Unsure)

3.3.7 Comparative Trust in Institutions

- Among the following governmental institutions or sectors, where would you rank fiscal governance in terms of perceived transparency and accountability? (1 being the highest and 5 being the lowest) (Healthcare/Education/Infrastructure/Defense/Fiscal governance))

3.3.8 Recommendations

- What specific measures or initiatives do you believe would enhance transparency and accountability in public finance? (Open-ended)

3.4 Data Analysis

The collected data was coded and entered into statistical software for analysis. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the data and provide an overview of the respondents' perceptions. Inferential statistics, such as chi-square tests and t-tests, were employed to identify significant differences in perceptions based on demographic variables like age, gender, and location.

Open-ended responses were analyzed using thematic analysis. Responses were read multiple times to identify common themes and patterns related to public perceptions of accountability and transparency.

3.5 Limitations

While the survey method offers numerous advantages, it's essential to acknowledge its limitations. The reliance on self-reported data can introduce biases, and there may be potential misinterpretations of questions by respondents. Additionally, while efforts were made to ensure a diverse sample, there might be segments of the population that are underrepresented.

4 Findings

4.1 Descriptive Statistics

Our dataset encompasses a diverse range of respondents, predominantly from the 35-44 age bracket. Most of our participants are male (85%), reflecting the gender distribution of the survey participants. A significant 90% of these respondents hail from urban areas, indicating the metropolitan-centric nature of our survey.

Figure 1: Distribution of the Transparency and Accountability Ratings

4.2 Perception of Transparency and Accountability

The transparency and accountability of public funds allocation in Bangladesh are rated, on average, just below 4 on a 10-point scale. This low median score, coupled with the observation that over 75% of respondents rate it 5 or below, underscores a prevailing sentiment of skepticism and concern among the populace. This sentiment is consistently observed across different age groups, with no significant variation in perception.

4.3 Awareness of Environmental Challenges

A striking observation from the dataset is the lack of awareness regarding environmental challenges. Approximately 59.4% of respondents are not cognizant of the environmental challenges faced by Bangladesh. This unawareness spans across genders, with both males and females showing similar patterns of ignorance.

4.4 Sectoral Trust and Transparency

When asked about which sector they perceived as the most transparent, a majority of respondents pointed towards the Defense sector. This is a noteworthy finding, hinting at the populace's faith in defense-related fiscal transactions compared to other sectors such as Healthcare, Education, or Infrastructure.

Figure 2: Awareness of Environmental Challenges

Figure 3: Perception of Transparency by Sector

Figure 4: Information Accessibility about Public Funds

Figure 5: Comparative Trust in Institutions

Figure 6: Transparency Perception by Age Group

Figure 7: Awareness of Environmental Challenges by Gender

4.5 Information Accessibility

A salient observation from our dataset is the pronounced lack of information accessibility. Over 90% of respondents, both from urban and rural backgrounds, feel they are not adequately informed about the allocation, management, and utilization of public funds. This finding accentuates the need for better communication and transparency mechanisms.

Figure 8: Awareness of Environmental Challenges by Gender

4.6 Comparative Trust in Institutions

A comparative analysis of trust across various institutions showcases a consistent pattern. The Defense sector is the outlier, with the highest trust rating, while sectors like Healthcare, Education, Infrastructure, and Fiscal Governance all grapple with similarly low trust ratings.

4.7 Correlation Analysis

A deeper dive into the correlation between transparency perception and trust in different sectors reveals weak linear relationships. The values, being close to zero, indicate that the general perception of transparency does not necessarily dictate the trust in individual sectors.

5 Conclusion

In the intricate tapestry of Bangladesh’s socio-economic landscape, the threads of public finance, transparency, and trust are interwoven intricately. This research sought to unravel these threads and examine the perceptions of the Bangladeshi populace regarding transparency and accountability in the allocation of public funds. Our findings underscore a palpable sentiment of skepticism among the respondents. With the average rating of transparency and accountability in public funds allocation hovering just below 4 on a 10-point scale, the trust deficit becomes evident. This sentiment extends to various sectors, with Defense being an outlier, enjoying relatively higher trust among the populace. The overarching lack of awareness regarding environmental challenges, coupled with pronounced information inaccessibility, further accentuates the need for enhanced communication mechanisms and greater public engagement. From a global perspective, the importance of transparency and accountability in public finance has been well-acknowledged, with transparent fiscal management being linked to enhanced government credibility and efficient resource allocation. Yet, in the context of Bangladesh, a disconnect persists. While initiatives like the establishment of climate change trust funds highlight the government’s proactivity, their effectiveness is often contingent upon public perception and trust. As this research reveals, there remains significant room for improvement in this realm. The unanimous desire for greater public engagement underscores the populace’s yearning for a more inclusive decision-making process. In a democratic framework, where governance rests on the pillars of public trust and participation, these findings hold profound implications. They beckon towards a more inclusive, transparent, and accountable approach to fiscal governance, one where the citizenry is not just passive observers but active participants in the nation’s fiscal journey. Furthermore, the weak correlation between transparency perception and trust in individual sectors suggests that a more nuanced approach is required. It is not enough to merely enhance transparency; efforts must be directed towards fostering trust in specific sectors, addressing sector-specific challenges, and tailoring communication strategies accordingly. In conclusion, as Bangladesh navigates the challenges of the 21st century, the trust factor in public finance emerges as a critical determinant of its socio-economic trajectory. This research shines a light on the prevailing perceptions, offering insights that could guide future policy interventions, foster greater public involvement, and ultimately, build a more transparent, accountable, and resilient fiscal governance framework for the nation.

References

- [1] M Niaz Asadullah, Kazi Md Mukitul Islam, and Zaki Wahhaj. Child marriage, climate vulnerability and natural disasters in coastal bangladesh. *Journal of biosocial science*, 53(6):948–967, 2021.
- [2] Md Nazirul Islam Sarker, Min Wu, GM Monirul Alam, and Roger C Shouse. Livelihood vulnerability of riverine-island dwellers in the face of natural disasters in bangladesh. *Sustainability*, 11(6):1623, 2019.
- [3] Kashif Abbass, Muhammad Zeeshan Qasim, Huaming Song, Muntasir Murshed, Haider Mahmood, and Ijaz Younis. A review of the global climate change impacts, adaptation, and sustainable mitigation measures. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 29(28):42539–42559, 2022.
- [4] Ove Hoegh-Guldberg, Daniela Jacob, M Taylor, Tania Guillén Bolaños, Marco Bindi, Sally Brown, Ines Angela Camilloni, Arona Diedhiou, Riyanti Djalante, K Ebi, et al. The human imperative of stabilizing global climate change at 1.5 c. *Science*, 365(6459):eaaw6974, 2019.
- [5] Md Abdul Kaium Masud, Juichiro Sahara, and Md Humayun Kabir. A relationship between climate finance and climate risk: Evidence from the south asian region. *Climate*, 11(6):119, 2023.
- [6] Gemma Hayward and Sonja Ayeb-Karlsson. ‘seeing with empty eyes’: a systems approach to understand climate change and mental health in bangladesh. *Climatic Change*, 165(1-2):29, 2021.
- [7] Md Roushon Jamal, Paul Kristiansen, Md Jahangir Kabir, and Lisa Lobry de Bruyn. Challenges and adaptations for resilient rice production under changing environments in bangladesh. *Land*, 12(6):1217, 2023.
- [8] Gulsan Ara Parvin, Rajarshi Dasgupta, Md Anwarul Abedin, Masashi Sakamoto, Bingunath Ingirige, Mohammad Golam Kibria, Kumiko Fujita, Mrityika Basu, Rajib Shaw, and Hajime Nakagawa. Disaster experiences, associated problems and lessons in southwestern coastal bangladesh: exploring through participatory rural appraisal to enhance resilience. *Sustainable and Resilient Infrastructure*, 8(sup1):223–236, 2023.
- [9] Diana Escandon-Barbosa, David Urbano-Pulido, and Andrea Hurtado-Ayala. Exploring the relationship between formal and informal institutions, social capital, and entrepreneurial activity in developing and developed countries. *Sustainability*, 11(2):550, 2019.
- [10] Ian Shaw and Matthew Norton. Kinds and quality of social work research. In *Research and Social Work in Time and Place*, pages 116–132. Routledge, 2023.
- [11] Yuyue Yan and Tomohisa Hayakawa. Incentive design for noncooperative dynamical systems under sustainable budget constraint for pareto improvement. In *2022 American Control Conference (ACC)*, pages 580–585. IEEE, 2022.
- [12] Masna Sopia Silalahi and Sandhy Walsh. Analyzing government policies in addressing unemployment and em-powering workers: Implications for economic stability and social welfare. *Law and Economics*, 17(2):99–117, 2023.
- [13] Anggi Munarko. Determinants of service quality: Efficiency and workspace. *AKADEMIK: Jurnal Mahasiswa Humanis*, 2(3):136–144, 2022.
- [14] Grace Carswell and Geert De Neve. Transparency, exclusion and mediation: how digital and biometric technologies are transforming social protection in tamil nadu, india. *Oxford Development Studies*, 50(2):126–141, 2022.
- [15] Philipp Meyer. Transparency and strategic promotion: How court press releases facilitate judicial agenda-building in germany. *Public Relations Review*, 48(4):102228, 2022.
- [16] Sharofiddin Ashurov, Syed Musa bin Syed Jaafar Alhabshi, Anwar Hasan Abdullah Othman, Mohammad Habibullah, and Mohd Sukri Muhamad Yusof. Developing a conceptual framework for zakat collection and distribution impact on social welfare through implications of sdgs. In *Research anthology on measuring and achieving sustainable development goals*, pages 422–440. IGI Global, 2022.
- [17] Md Al-Mamun, Md Jamal Hossain, Morshed Alam, Md Shahin Parvez, Bablu Kumar Dhar, and Md Rabiul Islam. Discrimination and social exclusion of third-gender population (hijra) in bangladesh: A brief review. *Heliyon*, 2022.

- [18] Martin S Feldstein. Debt and taxes in the theory of public finance. In *Debt and Taxes in the Theory of Public Finance: Feldstein, Martin S.* [S1]: SSRN, 2022.
- [19] Musabber Ali Chisty, Maliha Muhtasim, Fariha Jahin Biva, Syeda Erena Alam Dola, and Nesar Ahmed Khan. Sendai framework for disaster risk reduction (sfdrr) and disaster management policies in bangladesh: How far we have come to make communities resilient? *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*, 76:103039, 2022.
- [20] Elizabeth L Cope, Marya Khan, and Sarah Millender. Trust in health care: Insights from ongoing research. *Health Affairs Forefront*, 2022.
- [21] Veronika Litovtseva, Dariusz Krawczyk, Aleksandra Kuzior, Maryna Brychko, and Tetiana Vasylieva. Marketing research in the context of trust in the public sector: A case of the digital environment. *Innovative Marketing*, 18(4):133–147, 2022.
- [22] Peter Ototsky, Sergey Manenkov, and Alexander Smoliak. Requisite trust requirements for digital society development. *Kybernetes*, 52(9):2958–2975, 2023.